

POLICY BRIEF

When Preparedness Gets an Address

*Mapping Proximity to Registered Public Shelters in
Norway*

For Decision-Makers #2 | June 2026

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Messages for Decision-Makers

More than half of Norway's population lives more than 2 km from a registered public shelter.

Registered public shelters are concentrated in southern Norway and around the Oslo Fjord.

Access to registered public shelters varies sharply between municipalities.

Several large municipalities, with more than 20,000 residents, have almost no nearby registered public shelter coverage.

Open geodata make it possible to analyze civil preparedness infrastructure in a transparent and place-based way.

12.9%
within 500 m

28.4%
within 1 km

48.0%
within 2 km

52.0%
more than 2 km away

Source: DSB/GeoNorge and SSB. Straight-line distances from 1 × 1 km population-grid cell centers.

National shelter totals hide a basic geography problem: registered public shelters are not located close to where most people live.

Policy timeline

1998 Last new public shelters were built
2022 Russia invades Ukraine; shelter debate accelerates
2023 NOU 2023:17 published
Jan 2025 White Paper (Meld. St. 9) proposes new building obligation

Nov 2025 Adressa: thousands of shelter places removed
Apr 2026 Government says consultation draft still being finalized
Jun 2026 Holmestrand Example in Holmestrand municipality where building a shelter was deferred due to cost
2026 New regulatory framework still pending

Background

Preparedness is not only about how much capacity a country has. It is also about where that capacity is located.

Norway is strengthening civil preparedness in response to a more uncertain security environment. The Total Preparedness White Paper (Meld. St. 9, 2024–2025) calls for stronger civilian resilience. The Total

Preparedness Commission (NOU 2023:17) describes a threat landscape shaped by geopolitical rivalry, technological vulnerability, climate change, and demographic change. In this context, civil protection infrastructure has returned to the political agenda.

Shelters are part of Norway's preparedness system, but the public shelter network is limited. The Norwegian Civil Defense reports almost 19,000 registered shelters, with space for about 2.5 million people. Most of these are

private shelters linked to specific buildings. Around 600 are registered public shelters, with approximately 300,000 places. No new public shelters have been built since 1998.

The Storting has asked the government to prepare for lifting the temporary exemption from the shelter-building obligation. In January 2025, the Total Preparedness White Paper proposed reinstating the requirement for new buildings over 1,000 square meters, including schools, hospitals, and residential buildings (NRK, 2025). DSB has estimated the additional construction cost at approximately NOK 30,000 per shelter place. In December 2025, the government said it was working on a consultation draft for new shelter regulations (Altinget, 2025).

Media reporting has also raised questions about whether registered shelter capacity is stable. Adressa (2025) reported that thousands of shelter places had been removed, including 2,000 places deleted through one administrative decision.

These developments form the background for this brief. The analysis below focuses on a narrower and directly measurable question: where are registered public shelters located in relation to where people live?

Shifting from capacity to geography

This brief asks a simple but underexamined question: how well does registered public shelter infrastructure align with where people actually live? To answer this, the analysis links three open datasets from GeoNorge: registered public shelters from DSB, population data on a 1×1 km grid from SSB, and municipality boundaries from Kartverket.

For each populated grid cell, the straight-line distance to the nearest registered public shelter was calculated. The result is a measure of geographic proximity to public shelter infrastructure. It does not measure shelter quality, capacity, maintenance, walking time, or actual accessibility in a crisis.

Figure 1. Registered public shelters in mainland Norway. Infrastructure is concentrated in the south and around the Oslofjord. Coverage thins markedly further north. Source: DSB/GeoNorge.

Most Norwegians live more than 2 km from a registered public shelter

The national pattern is uneven. Only 12.9% of the population lives within 500 meters of a registered public shelter, and 28.4% lives within 1 kilometer. At the other end of the distribution, 52.0% lives more than 2 kilometers away. Put differently, a majority of Norwegians do not have a registered public shelter in close proximity.

This Norwegian pattern is consistent with a broader finding from emergency infrastructure research: access gaps are often spatial, not merely numerical. Zhang et al. (2023) show that shelter access can vary systematically across rural and peri-urban areas, while Coleman et al. (2024) frame infrastructure resilience as an equity problem. The Norwegian contribution here is more specific: public shelter proximity varies sharply by place.

Figure 2. Population share by straight-line distance to the nearest registered public shelter. More than half of Norwegians fall in the highlighted red bar. The first three bands are cumulative. Source: DSB/GeoNorge and SSB; 1 × 1 km grid.

The municipal pattern is just as important as the national average. Several city municipalities have higher proximity shares. In many rural areas, especially in northern Norway, the share of residents within 1 km of a registered public shelter is close to zero. Among larger municipalities, defined here as those with at least 20,000 residents, several have no residents within 1 km, including Øygarden, Nittedal, Nesodden, Nes, Hå, and Eidsvoll.

Case in point: Holmestrand, 2026

In June 2026, Vestfold County Council reported that the new Harriet Backer upper secondary school in Holmestrand was being planned without a shelter. The project budget had risen from NOK 1.1 billion to NOK 1.44 billion. The shelter element alone was costed at NOK 38 million. The county director recommended proceeding without it, citing an approved dispensation and the expectation that the new national obligation would not take effect before the building permit is issued (Sande Avis, 2026).

The main committee voted unanimously to investigate state funding options for the shelter, with the final decision expected in the county assembly on June 16, 2026. The outcome remains open.

One case cannot prove a national pattern. It does, however, show the practical tension behind the policy debate: shelters are easier to

support in principle than to finance inside a strained construction budget. It also shows why the dispensation system matters for actual preparedness outcomes.

Who carries the burden of preparedness?

Geographic proximity is part of a larger distributional question. Norwegian authorities now recommend that as many people as possible be able to manage for one week in a crisis. The operational logic is understandable: in a serious crisis, municipalities and emergency services must prioritize people who cannot manage without help.

That shift is not neutral in how it falls. A household with savings, storage space, a car, and local networks is better placed to act on preparedness advice than a household with low income, limited storage, limited mobility, or few local ties. As argued elsewhere (Jacobsen, 2026a), household preparedness can quietly reproduce existing inequalities when more responsibility is devolved downward.

Public shelter geography matters for the same reason. Where registered public shelters are distant, households, municipalities, and local institutions must fill more of the gap through private shelters, local planning, evacuation capacity, or household preparedness. This analysis cannot show how that would work in a real attack or crisis. It does show where the public shelter network is thin relative to settlement patterns.

What this analysis does and does not show

These findings do not mean that Norway's overall civil protection system is inadequate. Public shelters are one part of a wider system that includes private shelters, possible future dekningsrom, household preparedness, warning systems, evacuation capacity, and local emergency planning. None of those elements are assessed here. The analysis also says nothing about whether registered shelters are well maintained, operationally ready, large enough, staffed, or accessible in a crisis. Eight

of 20 Civil Defense districts reportedly carried out no shelter inspections in 2025, with resource constraints cited as one possible explanation (Altinget, 2026). That dimension of the problem lies beyond the scope of geodata analysis.

What the analysis does is shift the question from how many shelters Norway has to who lives near registered public shelter infrastructure. That is a relevant, tractable, and underexamined dimension of Norwegian civil preparedness policy.

Recommendations

1. Map registered shelter infrastructure against population distribution

Municipal and national planners should regularly assess how registered public shelter coverage matches where people live now and where population growth is expected. This is especially important in growing municipalities where proximity to registered public shelters is currently low or close to zero.

2. Include geographic proximity in shelter investment decisions

When the new shelter obligation takes effect, planning should not be guided by total national capacity alone. Geographic proximity should be an explicit criterion for where new public capacity is built or upgraded.

3. Assess public funding mechanisms for shelter construction

The Holmestrand case suggests that NOK 38 million for a shelter can be a significant line item in a strained county budget. If the national obligation is to be meaningful in practice, state co-financing mechanisms should be assessed alongside the new regulatory framework. Leaving the full cost to private developers or strained local budgets may increase the risk of exemptions and deferrals.

4. Review the dispensation system

Before the new framework takes effect, authorities should review how often dispensations are granted, for what reasons,

and in what types of projects. This would clarify whether the temporary exemption has become a routine part of shelter policy in practice.

5. Use open geodata as a standard preparedness tool

The method used here links data from DSB, SSB, and Kartverket. It is transparent, replicable, and low-cost. It can help local and national authorities monitor whether public shelter infrastructure keeps pace with demographic change and should be integrated into routine preparedness planning.

6. Treat preparedness coverage as a distributional question

Where geographic gaps and social capacity gaps overlap, they can reinforce one another. Planners should identify places where thin public shelter infrastructure coincides with limited household or municipal capacity and address those vulnerabilities together rather than as separate problems.

Further reading

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Roy Aulie Jacobsen is a PhD Research Fellow in Political Communication at Kristiania University of Applied Sciences, Norway. His research examines crisis communication, platformization, and how preparedness policy and infrastructure align with population needs.

The analysis draws on open geodata and computational methods, combining perspectives from political science, crisis communication, and civil preparedness research. While grounded in the Norwegian context, the findings have broader relevance for European preparedness governance.

This brief reflects the author's independent analysis based on open data. It does not represent the official position of Kristiania University of Applied Sciences.

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Replication materials: <https://github.com/royaja/open-research-projects/tree/main/When%20Preparedness%20Gets%20an%20Address>

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